

CLASSROOM BEHAVIORAL MENUS IN A SELF-REGULATED LEARNING ENVIRONMENT TOWARDS AN IMPROVED SCIENCE COGNITIVE SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the effectiveness of Classroom Behavioral Menu (CBM) in response to a self-regulated environment caused by unexpected national and worldwide situations, calamities, and problems such as pandemic. Furthermore, this attempted to assess how CBM could improve the Cognitive Science Process Skills (CSPS) of students in a self-regulated environment such as distance learning. Using descriptive-developmental research design, the study assessed the importance of classroom behavioral menu in a self-regulated learning environment through the use of questionnaire which compose of different classroom behavioral menu. This research utilized a total of 100 respondents from G11 STEM students who take online learning in General Chemistry. For a depth analysis, the following were used to analyze the gathered data using made-questionnaire: frequency distribution, compute for the weighted mean, ranking and composite mean. Moreover, the study will utilize pretest and posttest where scores on both tests of the students were used to determine the effectiveness of the application of CBM in a self-regulated environment. The null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference related to students' scores between their pre-test and post-test relatively about their cognitive science processes skills was not sustained. Moreover, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between students' classroom behavioral menu and the students' cognitive science processes skills was not sustained.

Keywords: classroom behavioral menu, self-regulated, cognitive science process skills